

as morality and edification, without this element, these stories would not have made sense and the power with which they touch the soul.

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DIFFICULTIES OF POETIC TRANSLATION IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

G`ofurova Nazokat Komiljonovna

Teacher of the National University of Uzbekistan
National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent

Abstract: This article gives peculiarities of poetic translation in Uzbek and English languages with examples in turn. As these two languages belong to different language families, translators may face various difficulties while they are translating literary poets. Rhymed words, inversion and other stylistic devices are main essences of poetry so translators must follow the rhythm, musical-literary tune in poems. Although poetic translation seems more complicated than prosaic translation, it is one of the developing fields in translation.

Keywords: poetic and prosaic types of literature, lyrical hero, character, lines, poetry, emotional and spiritual expression, rhyme, intonation, musical tune

Although translation may seem as a collection of words at first, it requires more commitment and ability of choosing the right word in the right place. Translation is also considered as an international communication of literary works. Literary works can be divided into poetic and prosaic types. Though lots of prosaic works are being translated into Uzbek language nowadays, poetic translations of Uzbek poets' poems or the translations of well – known foreign poets' works are more complicated and it demands special poetic and literary ability from the translator for creating the real “copy” of the original literary poetic product.

Poem – is a delicate example of an emotional and spiritual expression of a poet. Poems deliver not only the mood, horizon and inner world of authors, but also they convey some conclusions about the culture, tradition and atmosphere of the period they are created. Poetry cannot be compared with prose in literature. They both have different roles and responsibilities in the field of literature. Poetry expresses the feeling, thought and conclusions of its author so gracefully that it can touch readers' heart and even make the readers feel as the same way the authors do. Poems have a great aesthetic power of effecting to people, or in another word, they give some lyrical mood while reading. Special poetic intonations in this type of literary work increases the value of poetry.

Poetic translation is a complicated process. It is not only translating the words into another language, but also it means to deliver the meaning and feeling, following the rhythm, intonation and other demanding necessities of the current poem in turn. The composition and the expression every poem must suit and fulfill each other. Here is an example by Nicholas Gordon:

After you leave, I will become a tree
Alone on a hillside, loving wind and sun,
Waiting for you to return home to me
Though centuries of lonely stars may run.

Here the poet chose tree and me, sun and run rhymed words to create a poem. This short extract of the poem just gives a meaning of absence of the lyrical hero of the poem. The hero looks like a tree that stays at the same place all the time. If you think deeper, you may notice that, the tree is a character in love and he/she wishes to finish the heart – rending and long-lasting absence. Therefore, he/she is going to stay on a hill to see the beloved person. If the translator doesn't have a special ability and understanding of poetry, they cannot translate poems at all. This is the first problem of poetic translation in literature. The rhyme, meaning, lyrical hero must be conveyed correctly and skillfully into another language. Here is a translation into Uzbek:

Sen ketgach, daraxtga qolay aylanib,
Qoyada bir o`zim qaytishing kutib.
Shamol-u quyoshga berib qalbimni
O`tsa-da asrlar kutay qon yutib.

The last words of every couplet here suits and tries to give the same meaning as the original author of the poem. In this translation the lyrical hero wants to be an alone tree and to stay on a hill hoping to see his/her beloved person's arrival. The character is so keen on to see the lover that, he/she can wait for centuries with patience.

The poet continues to “swim” in his thoughts here again:

I'll grow tall and give lots of shade,
Sheltering birds and other bright-eyed things.
Pleased with all the progress that I've made,
I'll spread my leafy branches out like wings.

The tree will grow taller and taller as the absence lasts. However, the lyrical hero never loses hope and doing some good showing his/her generosity. The stretched branches of the tree are just like a dimly hope of the character to catch the beloved whenever he/she meets on the way, presumably. And the translation says:

Men esa o`saman berib soyalar
Qushlar, xasharotga bo`lay boshpana.

Shodlanib shoxlarim cho`zay har yonga,

Yaproqli novdalar qanotim – mana.

Every line of the original version has been conveyed and translated clearly in its Uzbek translation. As the absence of the lover lasts, the persistence and feelings of the lyrical hero increases higher and higher. But the character in the poem is still gazing all around the way waiting for his/her beloved person's arrival. However, in the last lines we see some hopelessness a little bit pessimistic mood of the lyrical character:

But oh! Every moment of every day

I'll miss you much with the passion of the wind,

Gazing endlessly upon the way

That without you must empty, empty wind.

The passion is growing longer as days pass. But still no news of his beloved. The poet finishes the poem looking at the endless ways of this complicated life. He has last energies of hope to see the arrival of his lover. As we see impatience and hopelessness is approaching and invading the hero of love. This is the translation:

E voh! Taassuf-ki har lahza, har on,

Sog'inch qiynar meni shamolday buyuk.

Adoqsiz yo`llarga termulganimcha

Sog'inch meni qiynar sen menga suyuk.

If the glimmer of depression is expressed by the saying of: “But oh!” expression in English, this feeling is given in Uzbek by the expression of: “E voh!” which shows the dark sides of the hero of this lyrical genre.

Poetic translation includes a complicated literary process. Translators of poetic-lyrical genres usually have to try harder as compared to the translators of prosaic genres. Therefore, we can absolutely call these types of poetic creators as translator-poets in the field of translation. Poetic translation is a process of its author and it is done successfully when something inspires and motivates to write and create a real literary work. Or in other case, the poet loses its value and it is not accepted well by readers. However, it cannot be denied that, poetic translation is a

work of heard and soul. Because a translator only can translate or “reproduce” a poem when he/she sees some harmonization, when he/she feels the same way as lyrical hero feels.

One of the main difficulties of poetic translation in literature is grammatical and structural differences of two different languages as well. So lots of translators may fail when they face poetic translation. Sequences of parts of speech can absolutely vary in languages and poetic translation is not only conveying the meaning and main idea of any kind of poem, but also it is providing the musical tone, rhythmical figure and following all rules that help to create a poem.

Inversion is one of the necessary factors of poetry. It usually differentiates a poem from a prosaic work. So poetic translators must have good knowledge of the language they are translating into. Inversion, repetition, chiasm, rhetorical questions and parallelism are all considered as special providers of poetry.

Poetic translation from Uzbek into English or from English into Uzbek is a complicated process and rarely done till today. However, we can say that, some rubais of Navoi have been translated into English:

Ko‘z birla qoshing yaxshi, qabog‘ing yaxshi,

Yuz birla so‘zing yaxshi, dudog‘ing yaxshi.

Eng birla menging yaxshi, saqog‘ing yaxshi,

Bir-bir ne deyin, boshdin-ayog‘ing yaxshi.

Q. Ma‘murov translates this rubai:

Your eyes and brows are good, eyelids are good,

Your appearance and words are good, your lips are good,

Your cheeks with marks are good, chins are good,

Shall I name one by one, you are good from head to foot.

We can confidently say that, the translator has successfully given all meaning and feeling of the lyrical poem.

As a conclusion, we may say that Uzbek vocabulary is rich of synonyms, homonyms, antonyms, syntactic and stylistic devices and other grammatical

structures. So it won't be a problem to find the necessary equivalent of a word to translate.

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CHET TILINI O`QITISHDA “LOYIHA USTIDA ISHLASH”NING AFZALLIKLARI

Исраилова Дилором Шомахаматовна
ЎзДЖТУ, немис тили назарий фанлар кафедраси
dilorom_76@mail.ru +998935392655

Annotatsiya: Chet tilini o`qitishda ananaviy mashg`ulotlardan biroz chekinib zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan keng foydalangan xolda noananaviy mashg`ulotlar olib borilishi bugungi kunda talabalarda til o`rganishga bo`lgan qiziqishni oshirmoqda. Ushbu maqolada talabalarda til o`rganishga bo`lgan motivatsiyani oshirishda o`qituvchining roli va noan`anaviy vazifalardan biri bo`lgan “Loyiha ishi” haqida gap boradi.

Kalit so`zlar: Loyiha ishi, noan`anaviy mashg`ulot, ijodiy yondoshish, talabalar, zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar, samaradorlikni oshirish.